

A central heating network thermal-hydraulic calculation in
an individual house

LogiSTHer Software : the solved equations

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Abstract

A thermal-hydraulic steady state calculation - simultaneous calculation of the hydraulic and the thermal behaviour - of a central heating network in a individual house is carried out. This calculation, in which the whole hydraulic circuits constituting the computational domain are taken into account **simultaneously**, lasts about 60 seconds for a network including two parallel circuits. If the studied network contains only one circuit, the calculation is very fast. The calculation is performed on a standard laptop PC using free softwares.

A **comprehensive method** is presented, including the making the equations, describing their discretization and their numerical resolution, and finally an analysis of the results.

Thus, the pressure and the temperature at any point of the network, the flow rates through each radiator and the assumed uniform temperature of any element of the network are calculated, as a function of the whole input datas (geometry, pressure and thermal losses) which can vary independently of one another.

By integrating the calculated heating power, it is possible, using the Degree-Day datas which is an available meteorological data, to **predict the consumed energy** over a period of time and to provide the *energy mark*, from **A** to **E**, *according to the French regulation*.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

We wish to perform a steady-state thermal-hydraulic simultaneous calculation of the hydraulic and the thermal behaviour of a central heating network in a house. We build first the equations that govern hydraulics, that are solved numerically. Then numerical results are checked by comparison to those obtained in cases where an analytical solution exists. Furthermore, the generalisation to a real central heating network in a house is investigated. Firstly, the thermal aspect is dealt with, then the thermal aspect consists in the writing of the equations and their numerical resolution. The overall methodology of the hydraulic and thermal coupled calculation is then described and some results are provided. These results allow to design the boiler in terms of heating power. The energy aspect is also dealt with, using of a consumption criterion with respect to french regulations.

The overall datas (particularly from the radiators, the circulating pump and the mixing valve) has been available for any customers by the manufacturers through free websites.

A comprehensive methodology is shown, including writing the equations, their discretization, their numerical resolution and a discussion of the results. This methodology is implemented in the **LogiSther** software.

Chapter 2

Equations

2.1 Writing hydraulic equations et assumptions

Let us consider (cf. picture 2.1) a flow between two cross sections S and S' . The distance between these cross sections is dl , the center of gravity is G (elevation z) and G' (elevation $z+dz$), and the direction θ from horizontal axis. We call :

- p the pressure ;
- U the velocity ;
- ρ the specific weight ;
- g the gravitational acceleration ;
- F_f the friction forces.

We can apply the momentum theorem in the projection on the flow direction, that leads to the equation (2.1) :

$$\rho S U dU + S dp + S \rho dl g \sin(\theta) + dF_f = 0 \quad (2.1)$$

We transform the previous equation (2.1) using terms equivalent to a pressure, as we can see that $dl \sin(\theta) = dz$ and that we can define a friction pressure loss as $dP_f = \frac{1}{S} \cdot dF_f$. Thus, we can (cf. eq. (2.2)) integrate between two points A and B belonging to the circuit, considering that B is downstream A :

$$\int_{AB} \rho U dU + \int_{AB} dp + \int_{AB} \rho g dz + \Delta P_{fAB} = 0 \quad (2.2)$$

Figure 2.1 – Momentum theorem application

In the present study of a central heating in a house, the network is a closed circuit, so that the pressure forces $\int_{AB} dp$ in the equation (2.2) bring a zero contribution. Thus, we can transform the dynamic term of the equation (2.2) by dividing the circuit into several parts, each part having a constant cross section S_i :

$$\int_{AB} \rho U dU = \sum_i \left[\int_{S_i} \left(\frac{\dot{m}}{S_i} \right)^2 d \left(\frac{1}{\rho} \right) \right] \quad (2.3)$$

We also assume, since there is no mass sink, that the mass flowrate is constant in the present study. The driving pressure of the pump C is taken into account. The buoyancy term $F = -\int_{AB} \rho g dz$ is evaluated further in **Appendix A**, and we show here that the dynamic term is negligible. The equation (2.2) can be reduced to (cf. equation (2.4)) :

$$C + F = \Delta P_{fAB} \quad (2.4)$$

The total pressure drop ΔP_{fAB} (cf. eq. (2.5)) , between two points A and B located on the same streamline comes from two phenomena, the **regular** friction and the **singular** friction. The latter is due to local singularities of the pipe, i.e. sudden cross section change, bends, tees, valves , ... :

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \Delta P_{fAB} = \Delta P_{reg} + \Delta P_{sing} \\ \Delta P_{reg} = \Lambda \frac{L_{AB}}{D_h} \rho \frac{V^2}{2} \\ \Delta P_{sing} = k_{sing} \rho \frac{V^2}{2} \end{array} \right. \quad (2.5)$$

where :

- The dimensionless Reynolds number Re is equal to $\frac{\rho V D_h}{\mu}$;
- L_{AB} is the curvilinear distance between the two points A and B ;
- Λ is the regular friction coefficient ;
- D_h is the hydraulic diameter of the pipe ;
- k_{sing} is a singular pressure drop coefficient devoted to one singularity.

In some cases – i.e. the radiators – where the notion of bulk velocity is irrelevant, the previous relationship giving (cf. equation (2.5)) the singular pressure drop is replaced by $\Delta P_{sing} = \left(\frac{Q}{K_v}\right)^2$, where K_v is a specific dimensional coefficient and Q is the volumetric flowrate going through the singularity.

Mathematical functions, build from the thermodynamic look-up tables (BÁLINT Tibor[1]), are used to evaluate the specific weight ρ and the dynamic viscosity μ of the fluid (water), which both **depend on the temperature and the pressure**.

The regular friction coefficient depends on the kind of the flow regime, characterized by the Reynolds number, which can be laminar, fully turbulent or transitional between laminar and turbulent regimes. The turbulent regime type can be either **smooth** or **rough**, depending on the roughness of the wall. The friction coefficient Λ is written as :

- In laminar regime for Reynolds number less than 2300 : $\Lambda = 64 \cdot Re^{-1}$;
- A linear constitutive relation in transitional regime for Reynolds numbers between 2300 and 4000 ;
- In smooth turbulent regime, $\Lambda = 0.316 \cdot Re^{-0.25}$ for Reynolds numbers larger than 4000.

The friction law is shown on fig 2.2, in the case of a rough turbulent regime devoted to 3 values of relative roughness 10^{-2} , 10^{-3} and 10^{-4} , which satisfy the following implicit relationship of Coolebrook :

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{\Lambda}} = -2 \cdot \log_{10} \left(\frac{\epsilon}{3.7 \cdot D_h} + \frac{2.51}{Re \cdot \sqrt{\Lambda}} \right).$$

This equation depends on the Reynolds number Re , the hydraulic diameter D_h and the roughness ϵ . This equation is transformed as the following, in order to be solved numerically :

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{\Lambda^{(n+1)}}} = -2 \cdot \log_{10} \left(\frac{\epsilon}{3.7 \cdot D_h} + \frac{2.51}{Re \cdot \sqrt{\Lambda^{(n)}}} \right).$$

Figure 2.2 – Friction law

As a **thermal balance**, we assume the equality between the generated thermal power and the thermal losses to the outside of the calculated domain.

The computation will be iterative because the fluid equations and the thermal equations are coupled by the temperature.

2.2 Evaluation of the absolute pressure at any point

After the resolution of the equation (2.4), the **generalised Bernoulli relationship** will be used to evaluate the absolute pressure at any point. The circuit pressure reference is set by an expansion tank which is devoted to bear the thermal dilatation of the water. In our realistic case (cf. figure 4.1), the expansion tank is located on the suction side of the pump.

Let us write the steady state generalised Bernoulli relationship (cf. (2.6)) on a streamline. The flow is assumed to be **one-dimensional** and the fluid flows from the point 1 to the point 2, while these two points are located on both sides of the pump :

$$P_1 + \rho \frac{V_1^2}{2} + \rho g z_1 + C = P_2 + \rho \frac{V_2^2}{2} + \rho g z_2 + \Delta P_{12} \quad (2.6)$$

where :

- P is the pressure ;
- ρ is the specific weight **depending of the temperature and the pressure** ;
- g is the gravity ;

- V is the velocity ;
- z is the elevation ;
- ΔP_{12} is the total pressure drop between the point 1 and the point 2 (cf. equations (2.5)).
- C is the driving load of the pump.

One of the two chosen points will be the tee where the expansion tank is connected, where the pressure is imposed by the gaseous phase of the expansion tank.

Chapter 3

Analytical validation of the hydraulic calculation

3.1 General remarks

In this chapter, an analytical validation of the hydraulic calculation will be made on a simplified network. The unknown variables will be the volumetric flowrate q_i . The way in which this calculation is carried out allows to take into account simultaneously all the circuits.

3.2 Exemple 1 : pump feeding two sources of pressure drop installed in parallel

We will calculate the flowrates of a circuit consisting in a driving pump feeding two sources of pressure drop installed in parallel, depicted on figure 3.1 and characterized by the equations (3.1).

Figure 3.1 – Parallel network

$$\Delta P = k_1 \cdot q_1^2 = k_2 \cdot q_2^2 = F(Q) \quad (3.1)$$

where the pump characteristic $F(q)$ is defined by $F(q) = A + B \cdot q^2$.

We define the equivalent characteristic for both elements installed in parallel $k_{12} = \frac{k_1 k_2}{(\sqrt{k_1} + \sqrt{k_2})^2}$ and the analytical solution of the system (3.1) is :

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} q_1 = \sqrt{\frac{A \cdot k_{12}}{k_1 \cdot (k_{12} - B)}} \\ q_2 = \sqrt{\frac{A \cdot k_{12}}{k_2 \cdot (k_{12} - B)}} \\ Q = \sqrt{\frac{A}{k_{12} - B}} \\ \Delta P = \frac{A \cdot k_{12}}{k_{12} - B} \end{array} \right. \quad (3.2)$$

3.3 Exemple 2 : combined series/parallel connection

We will investigate a network containing a pump feeding two elements in series, while the second element consist in two elements is parallel, depicted on the figure 3.2 and determined by the equations (3.3).

Figure 3.2 – Combined series/parallel connection

$$\Delta P = k_0 \cdot Q^2 + k_1 \cdot q_1^2 = k_0 \cdot Q^2 + k_2 \cdot q_2^2 = F(Q) \quad (3.3)$$

where the pump characteristic $F(q)$ is also defined by $F(q) = A + B \cdot q^2$.

We define the same equivalent characteristic for the elements installed in parallel $k_{12} = \frac{k_1 k_2}{(\sqrt{k_1} + \sqrt{k_2})^2}$ and the analytical solution of the system (3.3) is :

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} q_1 = \sqrt{\frac{A \cdot k_{12}}{k_1 \cdot (k_0 + k_{12} - B)}} \\ q_2 = \sqrt{\frac{A \cdot k_{12}}{k_2 \cdot (k_0 + k_{12} - B)}} \\ Q = \sqrt{\frac{A}{k_0 + k_{12} - B}} \\ \Delta P = \frac{A \cdot (k_0 + k_{12})}{k_0 + k_{12} - B} \end{array} \right. \quad (3.4)$$

3.4 Numerical resolution of the equations

The equations (3.1) and (3.3) can be written in a **linear matrix format** $M \cdot X = Y_0$, while Y_0 is a constant term (respectively in systems (3.5) and (3.6)):

$$\begin{pmatrix} k_1 q_1 & 0 & -BQ \\ k_1 q_1 & -k_2 q_2 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} q_1 \\ q_2 \\ Q \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} A \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.5)$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} k_1 q_1 & 0 & (k_0 - B) \cdot Q \\ k_1 q_1 & -k_2 q_2 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} q_1 \\ q_2 \\ Q \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} A \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.6)$$

Then the solution – the volumetric flowrates – can be calculated by an matrix (M) inversion method : $X = M^{-1} \cdot Y_0$.

3.5 Numerical application

The main input parameters are provided in the table 3.1 and the main results are provided in the table 3.2.

k_0	k_1	k_2	A	B
1851.9	5555.6	11111.2	45000.	-5000.

Table 3.1 – Input parameters for the networks

Réseau	Q_1	Q_2	$Q_1 + Q_2$	ΔP
	m^3/h			Pa
Parallel	1.4953	1.0573	2.5526 (*)	12421.
Serie/parallel	1.3278	0.9389	2.2667	19310.

(*) Intersection of the *pump* curve and the *circuit12* curve on the figure 3.3

Table 3.2 – Results for parallel and serie/parallel networks

Figure 3.3 – Curves related to the pump and the serie/parallel circuit

3.6 Part conclusion

We have shown that, in two simple cases where an analytical solution exists, the numerical method leads to a value which converge to this solution. This method will be now applied to a complex hydraulic network, including the resolution of the coupled thermal problem.

Chapter 4

Generalisation to a complex heating network

4.1 General remarks

The investigated installation is a two storey house built in 1978, from which cold and hot manifolds are just under the intermediate ceiling. No pipe is installed outside in order to minimize the heat losses. As this method has been previously (cf. §3) implemented on an elementary network, the whole elements of the network are taken into account simultaneously.

4.2 Hydraulic calculation

We will now describe the equations that lead to study the realistic network. The gravity component is negligible because the network is a **closed** circuit.

Let us write the polynomial equation of the pump $F(Q) = a_n Q^n + \dots + a_2 Q^2 + a_1 Q + a_0$ providing the driving pressure of the pump, depending on the volumetric flowrate Q which goes through that pump. In the present study, we have taken $n = 5$.

Figure 4.1 – Realistic circuit

The figure 4.1 provides an illustration of the calculated realistic circuit. If N_R is the **numbers of radiators**, there are N_R hydraulics paths available for the fluid, which all have the same pressure drop. Then we can write the N_R following equations :

- The equation **1** means the equality between the pump driving pressure $F(Q) =$ and the pressure drop of the circuit [pump - A_1 - radiator 1 - R_1 - heater] ;
- The equation **2** means the equality between the pump driving pressure [A_1 - radiateur 1 - R_1] and the pressure drop of the circuit [A_1 - A_2 - radiator 2 - R_2 - R_1] ;
- The equation **3** means the equality between the pump driving pressure [A_1 - radiateur 1 - R_1] and the pressure drop of the circuit [A_1 - A_2 - A_3 -radiator 3 - R_3 - R_2 - R_1] ;
- ...

- The equation \mathbf{N}_R means the equality between the pump driving pressure $[A_1 - \text{radiateur } 1 - R_1]$ and the pressure drop of the circuit $[A_1 - A_2 - \dots - A_{N_R} - \text{radiateur } N_R - R_{N_R} - \dots - R_2 - R_1]$.

N_R **additional unknown** $Q_j, j = 1 \text{ à } N_R$ has been added to simplify the equations form :

- The equation $2N_R + 1$ is the equality $Q = \sum_{i=1}^{N_R} q_i$;
- ...
- The equations $N_R + 2 \text{ à } 2N_R$ are the equalities $Q_i = Q - q_i$;
- ...

As previously, the equations can be written in a **linear matrix format** $M \cdot X = Y_0$, while Y_0 is a constant term and X are the unknown flowrates. The latter are **mass** flowrates because the temperature is not uniform in any point. The details of the resolution of the equations system is reported in appendix B, and it can be seen that M is a square matrix and its dimension is $2N_R$. This appendix provides the form of the rows and the columns of the matrix M . Two types of row can be found in this matrix : firstly, the rows related to the equations of mass flowrate conservation which contain only 0, -1 and 1 values, and, secondly, the rows related to the pressure drop equality equations which contain only 0 value or real non zero value expressed as $c_{i,j}$. The latter are the singular and/or regular pressure drop of the whole elements belonging to the studied network.

If the studied network contains only one circuit, the previous matrix equation becomes a simple polynomial equation, leading to look for the roots of a 5th degree polynomial.

4.3 Thermal calculation

4.3.1 Temperature of two converging streams

Figure 4.2 – Converging streams

We want to determine the temperature of two pipes AC and BC converging in the pipe CD (cf. figure 4.2). In the case of cooling of AC by BC , that means if $T_B < T_A$, we write that the heat power transferred by the section of pipe AC is equal to the heat power received by the section of pipe BC : $\dot{m}_{AC} \cdot Cp \cdot (T_A - T_C) = \dot{m}_{BC} \cdot Cp \cdot (T_C - T_B)$, which can be written as :

$$T_C = \frac{\dot{m}_{AC} \cdot T_A + \dot{m}_{BC} \cdot T_B}{\dot{m}_{AC} + \dot{m}_{BC}} \quad (4.1)$$

In the case of heating of AC by BC , that means if $T_B > T_A$, we write that the heat power transferred by the section of pipe BC is equal to the heat power received by the section of pipe AC :

$\dot{m}_{AC} \cdot Cp \cdot (T_C - T_A) = \dot{m}_{BC} \cdot Cp \cdot (T_B - T_C)$, which can write into the same previous equation (4.1).

CD the resulting section of pipe of the convergence of AC and BC is characterized by the upstream temperature T_C (cf. (4.1)) and the mass flowrate $\dot{m}_{AC} + \dot{m}_{BC}$.

4.3.2 Internal heat exchanges

We assume that each room is closed, independant one from another, that means that the internal heat transfers between two rooms are negligible in comparison with the heat losses to the outside.

4.3.3 Thermal regulation of the heater

We do not proceed to a thermal calculation of the heater, but we assume that the hot downstream temperature is imposed, that reflects the existing thermal regulation.

4.3.4 Heat losses to the outside

We only consider the heat losses by convection and we assume that heat exchange by conduction – thermal bridge – is not significant.

In the equations, we use the term $H \cdot S$, which is the product of the global heat exchange coefficient with the area involved, to characterize each heat exchange with an outside wall.

We assume that the wall consists in an insulator (conductivity λ_{isol} and thickness e_{isol}) and stone (conductivity λ_{mur} and thickness e_{mur}) placed in series. Besides, T_{int} is the contact temperature between the stone and the insulator. The expression of the power P going through the assembly of the two materials, which have the same area S , satisfies the two following equations (cf. (4.2)) :

$$P = \frac{\lambda_{isol} \cdot S}{e_{isol}} \cdot (T_1 - T_{int}) = \frac{\lambda_{isol} \cdot S}{e_{isol}} \cdot (T_{int} - T_2) \quad (4.2)$$

Let us eliminate T_{int} , then we can write :

$$P = \frac{S \cdot (T_1 - T_2)}{\left(\frac{e_{isol}}{\lambda_{isol}} + \frac{e_{mur}}{\lambda_{mur}} \right)} \quad (4.3)$$

We see that the global heat exchange coefficient H_{global} of two elements in **series** satisfies the following relationship :

$$\frac{1}{H_{global}} = \frac{e_{isol}}{\lambda_{isol}} + \frac{e_{mur}}{\lambda_{mur}} .$$

In the case of a wall containing a window, let us define :

- T_1 and T_2 as the inside and outside wall temperature ;
- S_{tot} and S_w as the wall and window heat exchange surfaces;
- H_{global} and U_w as respectively the heat exchange coefficient of the wall and of the window;
- Φ_1 etand Φ_2 as respectively the power transfered through the wall firstly without window, and secondly the power transfered through the window. $\Phi = \Phi_1 + \Phi_2$ is the total transfered power.

In the wall and the windows are in **parallel**, we can write the following equations (cf. (4.4)) :

$$\begin{cases} \Phi_1 = H_{global} \cdot (S_{tot} - S_w) \cdot (T_1 - T_2) \\ \Phi_2 = U_w \cdot S_w \cdot (T_1 - T_2) \\ \Phi = \Phi_1 + \Phi_2 = ((H_{global} \cdot (S_{tot} - S_w) + U_w \cdot S_w) \cdot (T_1 - T_2)) \end{cases} \quad (4.4)$$

Some orders of magnitude will be given further is appendix C.

4.3.5 Heat loss along a pipe

Figure 4.3 – Heat loss along a pipe

A heat balance (cf. fig 4.3) is made on a part of a pipe which length is L (along the axis x), which radius is R , which a mass flowrate \dot{m} runs through it, and which H is the global thermal heat transfer coefficient with the outside at the temperature T_0 :

$$-\dot{m} \cdot Cp \cdot dT = H \cdot 2\pi R \cdot dx \cdot (T - T_0) \quad (4.5)$$

After integration along the pipe, the following equation can be written, in which the subscripts E and S are respectively related to the input and the output of the pipe :

$$\frac{T_S - T_0}{T_E - T_0} = \exp\left(-\frac{H \cdot 2\pi R \cdot L}{\dot{m} \cdot Cp}\right) \quad (4.6)$$

4.3.6 Thermal calculation in each room

The room temperature T_0 is the unknown. The power emitted by a radiator, including convection and radiation transfers, are provided by the manufacturer as look-up tables. Let us define ΔT by $\Delta T = \frac{T_E + T_S}{2} - T_0$, as T_E and T_S are respectively the input temperature and the output temperature of the radiator. The manufacturer assumes then that **the emitted power follows a non-linear law** $\Phi = \Phi_0 \cdot \Delta T^n$, as Φ_0 and n are two constant values defined for each radiator type. The constant value Φ_0 is provided by a calibration process. The exponent value is in general close to 1.3. We will further in appendix C that a justification of this power law can be made.

We will now consider the **case of two radiators in a room**. The unknowns are the same input temperature T_E , the two output temperatures T_{S1} and T_{S2} and the two mass flowrates \dot{m}_1 and \dot{m}_2 flowing through the radiators. We assume a new linear relationship between the thermal powers of the radiators, using a new input parameter α .

If H_2 is the heat transfer coefficient and S_2 is the heat exchange surface, the following equations has to be solved (cf. eq. (4.7)) :

$$\begin{cases} \Phi = \Phi_0 \cdot \Delta T_1^n + \Phi_0 \cdot \Delta T_2^n = H_2 \cdot S_2 \cdot (T_0 - T_{ext}) \\ \Phi = \dot{m}_1 \cdot Cp \cdot (T_E - T_{S1}) + \dot{m}_2 \cdot Cp \cdot (T_E - T_{S2}) \\ \dot{m}_1 \cdot (T_E - T_{S1}) = \alpha \cdot \dot{m}_2 \cdot Cp \cdot (T_E - T_{S2}) \end{cases} \quad (4.7)$$

We can write the following equations (cf. eq. (4.8)) which can be solved numerically after a linearization step and having written them in a matrix form :

$$\begin{pmatrix} \left(\begin{array}{ccc} -\Phi_0(\Delta T_1^{n-1} + \Delta T_2^{n-1}) - H_2 S_2 & \frac{1}{2} \Phi_0 \Delta T_1^{n-1} & \frac{1}{2} \Phi_0 \Delta T_2^{n-1} \\ -H_2 S_2 & -\dot{m}_1 Cp & -\dot{m}_2 Cp \\ 0 & -\dot{m}_1 & \alpha \dot{m}_2 \end{array} \right) \cdot \begin{pmatrix} T_0 \\ T_{S1} \\ T_{S2} \end{pmatrix} \\ \left(\begin{array}{c} -\Phi_0(\Delta T_1^{n-1} + \Delta T_2^{n-1}) \frac{T_E}{2} - H_2 S_2 T_{ext} \\ -(\dot{m}_1 + \dot{m}_2) Cp T_E - H_2 S_2 T_{ext} \\ (-\dot{m}_1 + \alpha \dot{m}_2) T_E \end{array} \right) \end{pmatrix} = \quad (4.8)$$

An additional term has to be inserted in the previous equations to take into account **ventilation losses**. This term is the quantity $\rho_{air} Cp_{air} \frac{V_{air}}{T_{ren_{air}}}$, as V_{air} being the air volume to

renew for a given period of time $Tren_{air}$.

An additional convection resistance is taken into account on each side of the wall, which we assume that follows a non-linear law $h_c \Theta^{n_c}$, with $n_c = 0.25$ and h_c being constant values (between 6 and 30 for inside convection et between 30 and 300 for outside convection).

On the figure 4.4, we have depicted two materials of thickness e_1 and e_2 in series (the conductivity of the first material is larger than the conductivity of the second one). We add two more unknowns, the inner wall temperature T_{pI} and the outer wall temperature T_{pE} . As on the figure 4.4, we only calculate the two temperatures T_{pI} and T_{pE} . The curved connection between T_0 and T_{pI} and the curved connection between T_{pE} and T_{ext} are non realistic drawing effects, since, in the present one-dimensional calculation model, the thermal boundary layer is not investigated. The term $H2 \cdot S2$ becomes (cf. eq. (4.9)) :

$$H2 \cdot S2 = \rho_{air} C_{p_{air}} \frac{V_{air}}{Tren_{air}} + \frac{1}{h_{c_{int}} \cdot (T_0 - T_{pI})^{n_c - 1} + H2S2_{pièce} + h_{c_{ext}} \cdot (T_{pE} - T_{ext})^{n_c - 1}} \quad (4.9)$$

Figure 4.4 – Convection effect

4.4 Structure of the global coupled calculation

The global calculation is divided into three successive phases : the hydraulic phase (cf §4.2), the thermal phase (cf 4.3.6) and an iterative process in order to evaluate the return temperatures and particularly the temperature upstream the 4-ports valve (respectively points R_i and A_0 on the figure 4.1).

The temperature and the absolute pressure of each element of the investigated circuit will be calculated.

Each return temperature at the point R_i is the consequence of the convergence (cf §4.3.1) of the output branch of the radiator, which index is i , and of the previous return branch at the point R_{i+1} (cf figure 4.1). We assume (cf §4.3.3) that the hot output of the heater is a constant input parameter (point C on the figure 4.1) and that (cf §4.3.5) the temperature of the upstream side of each radiator are identical (points A_i on the figure 4.1). Besides, the temperature of the downstream side of the first radiator is equal to the general return temperature, also equal to the temperature of the cold side of the heater (respectively points R_1 , R_0 et F on the figure 4.1).

4.5 Results of the global calculation

Among the output parameters of the calculation, emphasis will be placed on the mass flowrate flowing through each radiator and on the temperature of each room assumed to be uniform.

The outside temperature (which is a boundary condition) chosen for the design is called *base temperature* which is an available meteorological data for every geographical region.

The main values are grouped in the table 4.1, including the transverse dimension of the radiators. The rotation speed of the pump is indicated on the figure 4.5 where the driving characteristics of the pump can be found.

Figure 4.5 – Driving characteristics of a generic pump

4-ports valve stroke	Temperature			Convection coefficient	
	Base °C	output heater °C	upstream 4-p V. °C	inside [6,30]	outside [30,300]
12	-5	80	50.5	6	30

Table 4.1 – Main values

The pump static head pressure, which represents the global pressure drop of the heating circuit, is equal to $2.9 mCE$. The margin with respect to the maximal static head of the pump is 40%. Besides, the main results are grouped in the table 4.2. We see also that (cf. appendix B) the mass flowrate is one of the main output parameters, which conservation, on a section of a pipe where the temperature is not uniform, is ensured.

Room number	Width mm Emittor	Aperture	Flowrate kg/h	Mean temperature $^{\circ}C$	HS_{Wall} $W/^{\circ}$	HS_{Global} $W/^{\circ}$	Power W
1	700	8/8	366.4	18.3	35.	29.5	686.
2	1100	4/8	179.2	20.7	35.	29.4	756.

Table 4.2 – Main results

We can see that, despite some radiator are wide open (aperture 8/8), the temperature of room 1 is not high enough with such a base temperature chosen for the design. The insulation of these rooms have then to be enhanced, rather than increasing the size of the emittor.

The water of the investigated network has to be heated up from 47.2 to 50° to counterbalance the online thermal losses ($345 W$) and the extracted power by the two emittors (686 and $756 W$).

Chapter 5

Conclusion

A thermal-hydraulic calculation of the realistic central heating network of an individual house has been carried out on a standard laptop PC using free softwares. The duration of the computation for a network including two circuits is about 60 secondes. If the studied network contains only one circuit, the calculation is very fast. Every hydraulic circuits constituting the computational domain are taken into account simultaneously. The carried out methodology allows coupling both hydraulic and thermal behaviours.

The thermal-hydraulic calculation allows to evaluate the pressure and the temperature on any point belonging to the circuit, the flowrates flowing in each radiator and the temperature assumed to be uniform in each room. All these output parameters depend on the input parameters (geometric, pressure drop and thermal), while any of them can be varied independently of each other.

By integrating the calculated heating power, it is possible, using the Degree-Day datas which is an available meteorological data, to **predict the consumed energy** over a period of time and to provide the *energy mark*, from **A** to **E**, *according to the French regulation*.

Appendix A

Justifications

We deal with the significance of the dynamic term and of the buoyancy term in the equation (2.4).

Firstly, we evaluate the dynamic term $\left(\frac{\dot{m}}{S}\right)^2 \cdot d \left(\frac{1}{\rho}\right)$ which is equal to 1.4 Pa and is not significant.

Secondly the buoyancy term is evaluated. On the elementary close loop (cf. figure A.1) including only a heater and a radiator, the integral buoyancy term $I_{C-A-R-B-C}$ is equal to zero and can be expressed as the sum of one integral concerning the hot circuit I_{C-A-R} and one integral concerning the cold circuit I_{R-B-C} .

Figure A.1 – Evaluation of the buoyancy term

We have (cf. equation (A.1)) :

$$\begin{aligned}
I_{C-A-R-B-C} &= I_{C-A-R} + I_{R-B-C} = 0 \\
I_{C-A-R} &= - \int_C^R \rho g dz \\
I_{R-B-C} &= - \int_R^C \rho g dz
\end{aligned} \tag{A.1}$$

We assume that, along each hot or cold portion, the specific weight has a constant value, respectively ρ_C and ρ_F . Let us call z_C and z_R the elevations of the heater and of the radiator concentrated on one point, and $h = z_R - z_C$. We can write (cf. équation (A.2)) :

$$\begin{aligned}
I_{C-A-R} &= -\rho_C \cdot g \cdot \int_C^R dz = -\rho_C \cdot g \cdot (z_R - z_C) \\
I_{R-B-C} &= -\rho_F \cdot g \cdot \int_R^C dz = -\rho_F \cdot g \cdot (z_C - z_R)
\end{aligned} \tag{A.2}$$

Since we have previously defined that $h = z_R - z_C$, it comes (cf. équation (A.3)) :

$$I_{C-A-R-B-C} = (\rho_F - \rho_C) \cdot g \cdot h \tag{A.3}$$

Under our conditions of pressure, we can write :

- The cold temperature = 50.4°, the specific weight $\rho_F = 987.9 \text{ kg/m}^3$;
- The hot temperature = 80°, the specific weight $\rho_C = 971.7 \text{ kg/m}^3$;
- The mean elevation $H = 1 \text{ m}$.

In our example, we have found that the buoyancy term of the part of the circuit where the heater is is equal to $\frac{\Delta\rho}{\rho} \cdot H \approx \mathbf{0.017 \text{ mCE}}$. This value can be compared to the pressure drop of this circuit, which equal to 0.188 mCE . This buoyancy term has to be subtracted in the equation concerning this circuit to the value of the pressure drop of this circuit, or, in a equivalent way, to place this value in the right side of the solved matrix equation $M \cdot X = Y_0$, in our case on the last row.

By comparison, Henri CHARLENT et Patrick AGOSTINI provide, in *Traité des Installations Sanitaires et Thermiques* ([3]), a value of the buoyancy term, equal to 0.6 mmCE per meter of elevation and per degree difference. The value : $\Delta P_{flott} = 0.01776 \text{ mCE}$ is calculated, which is very close to the value that we have previously calculated.

Appendix B

Calculation matrix in the general case

We provide in this appendix the form of the matrix equations system that is solved, which type is $M \cdot X = B$, and M is a square matrix of dimension $2N_R + 3$.

We linearize the polynomial expression of the pump driving pressure $F(Q) = Q \cdot G(Q) + a_0$, with $G(Q) = a_n Q^{n-1} + \dots + a_2 Q + a_1$, and the matrix and linearized form of the equations is what be seen on the equations (B.2)). The linearized singular and regular pressure drops (cf. equations (B.1), and the values from the tables B.1 , B.2 and B.3), are taken into account.

Description	Parameter	value	unit
Diameter in the heater room	D_{chauf}	30	<i>mm</i>
Diameter of the manifold	D_{col}	26	<i>mm</i>
Diameter of the tapping	D_{piq}	14	<i>mm</i>

Table B.1 – Realistic network datas

Aperture	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Max
$K_v m^3/h$	0.11	0.16	0.22	0.35	0.45	0.56	0.67	0.75

Table B.2 – Singular pressure drops of the radiators

Description	Parameter	Value	Scheme
Heater	k_{heater}	3.	
Radiator	$k_{radiator}$	5.	
90° bend	k_{90bend}	1.	
Separating stream tee	k_{sep}	1.5	
Converging stream tee	k_{conv}	2.0	

Table B.3 – Other coefficients k_{sing} of singular pressure drops

Each radiator is equipped with a control element enabling the hydraulic balance of the circuit. The table B.2, provided by the manufacturer, shows 8 positions, and the singular pressure drop of a radiator can be written in S.I. units : $\Delta P_{srad} = 10^5 \cdot \left(\frac{3600}{K_v}\right)^2 \cdot Q^2$. Coefficients of the pressure drops of other singularities are shown in the table B.3.

$$\begin{cases} C_{rég}(L, Q, D) = \Lambda \cdot \frac{L}{Dh} \cdot \rho(P, T) \cdot \frac{Q}{2 \cdot S^2} \\ C_{sing}(k_{sing}, Q, D) = k_{sing} \cdot \frac{Q}{2 \cdot S^2} \quad \text{ou} \quad 10^5 \cdot \left(\frac{3600}{K_v}\right)^2 \cdot Q \\ \text{avec } S = \pi \frac{D^2}{4} \quad \text{et} \quad Re = \frac{\rho(P, T) \cdot V \cdot Dh}{\mu(P, T)} \end{cases} \quad (\text{B.1})$$

The coefficient of regular pressure drop Λ involved in the first equation of the system (B.1) will be evaluated at each iteration, in order to discriminate the different flow regimes : laminar, turbulent and transitional between laminar and turbulent regimes.

$$\begin{pmatrix}
c_{11} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & c_{18} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
c_{21} & c_{22} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & c_{29} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
0 & c_{32} & c_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & c_{310} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
0 & 0 & c_{43} & c_{44} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & c_{411} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
0 & 0 & 0 & c_{54} & c_{55} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & c_{512} & 0 & 0 \\
0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & c_{65} & c_{66} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & c_{613} & 0 \\
0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & c_{76} & c_{77} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & c_{714} \\
1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\
0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\
0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1
\end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix}
q_1^{(n)} \\
q_2^{(n)} \\
q_3^{(n)} \\
q_4^{(n)} \\
q_5^{(n)} \\
q_6^{(n)} \\
q_7^{(n)} \\
Q^{(n)} \\
Q_1^{(n)} \\
Q_2^{(n)} \\
Q_3^{(n)} \\
Q_4^{(n)} \\
Q_5^{(n)} \\
Q_6^{(n)}
\end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix}
a_0 \\
0 \\
0 \\
0 \\
0 \\
0 \\
0 \\
0 \\
0 \\
0 \\
0 \\
0 \\
0 \\
0
\end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{B.2})$$

Only the first row of the solution vector is a non zero value, which is equal to the constant term a_0 from the polynomial expression of the pump driving pressure, the values of the other rows are zero values.

The rows of the matrix (cf. eq. (B.2)) which contain only values 0, 1 et -1 correspond to flow balance equations. Each row is devoted to a circuit for which the non zero values c_{ij} represent the singular/regular pressure drops of each element involved in the circuit. Besides, as the temperature is not uniform in the circuit, the output parameters will be the **mass flowrates**, which are the X vector of the unknown flowrates in the matrix equation $M \cdot X = Y_0$.

Appendix C

Calculation of the power transmitted by the radiators

We will attempt to give a justification to the general form of the non-linear relationship that yields to evaluate the power transmitted by the radiators.

If we can assume that the prevailing thermal-hydraulic condition is turbulent natural convection, the previous non-linear relationship can be explained. The non-dimensional exchange law (eq. (C.1)) can be expressed as the product of the three non-dimensional numbers Nusselt Nu , Prandtl Pr and Grasshof Gr :

$$Nu = 0.13 (Pr \cdot Gr)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (\text{C.1})$$

We can write that the emitted power by a radiator is equal to $W = h \cdot S \cdot \Delta T$, in which the whole constants are evaluated at the film temperature, which is equal to the half-sum between the outer wall temperature and the ambient temperature :

- The Nusselt number $Nu = \frac{h \cdot L}{\lambda}$;
- The Prandtl number $Pr = \frac{\mu \cdot C_p}{\lambda}$, which is equal 0.7 for gas ;
- The Grasshof number $Gr = \frac{g \cdot \beta \Delta T L^3}{\nu^2}$
- h is the heat exchange coefficient to be found ;
- S is the heat exchange surface ;
- L is a characteristic length, which can be taken to the height of the considered radiator ;
- λ is the thermal conductivity ;
- C_p is the specific heat ;
- μ and ν are the dynamic kinematic viscosities ;
- g is the gravity acceleration ;

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- β is the thermal expansion coefficient, which is equal to $\frac{1}{T_{absolute}}$ for gas ;

The equation (C.1) can be re-written as the equation (C.2) :

$$W = 0.13 \cdot \lambda \cdot S \cdot \left(\frac{Pr_{Air} \cdot g \cdot \beta}{\nu^2} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \cdot \Delta T^{\frac{4}{3}} \quad (C.2)$$

If we assume that there is a little change in the thermal constants when the temperature rises from 20 °C to 50 °C, we can write the non-linear expression $W = K \cdot \Delta T^{\frac{4}{3}}$, in which K is constant. Besides, the exponent value $\frac{4}{3}$ is close to the value of about 1.3 which is measured by the radiators manufacturers.

Appendix D

Consumed energy - Degree-Day datas

If we assume that there is the same temperature T_0 in every rooms of the house being thermally investigated, and if T_{ext} is the outside temperature, the heat power lost through the walls is $W_{lost} = HS_{cumul} \cdot (T_0 - T_{ext})$, with $HS_{cumul} = 58.9 W/^\circ$ which was previously evaluated. The consumed energy is the integral of the power over the period of time $T_{heating}$ during the heating season, which can be written as shown in equation (D.1) :

$$E_{consumed} = \int_{T_{heating}} W_{lost} dt = HS_{cumul} \int_{T_{heating}} (T_0 - T_{ext}) dt \quad (D.1)$$

On the Web, there are a lot of documents relating to housing energy balances, and are, therefore, not dealt with in this document. Generally, the difference between an inside temperature of 20° and the selected threshold of 18° is considered as there are provided by free heating (i.e. sun, ...). So we consider that $T_0 = 18^\circ$.

The integral $\int_{T_{heating}} (T_0 - T_{ext}) dt$ is a meteorological data. If the outside temperature is above 18° , this term brings no contribution to the integral. This quantity (called Degree-Day datas) is generally not available for free, but it is available for free on certain websites (i.e. cf. [4]).

A common definition of the Degree-Day is the difference, on a period of time, between the threshold of 18° and the arithmetical mean of the minimum temperature and the maximum temperature. For a periodic (period T) sine wave phenomenon which is a function of the time t having the form $y(t) = a_0 + a \sin(\frac{2\pi t}{T})$, the mean $\int_T y dt$ is exactly equal to a_0 .

We can write over one year, with respect to the relevant units (cf. equation (D.2)) :

$$E_{kWh/year} = HS_{cumul}/1000 \cdot 24 \cdot [Degree - Day number] \quad (D.2)$$

In the table D.1, we provide a prediction of the consumed energy over one year, and the energy per unit of area is evaluated in our example for which the living area is up to $148 m^2$. According to the French Regulations which provide standards that everyone have to fulfil for each

house (cf. table D.2) we have evaluated the marks B to C , providing a low energy consuming network.

evaluated period of time	nombre DJU $^{\circ} \cdot day$	Energy kWh	Energy/ m^2 kWh/m^2	Mark tableD.2
1/10/2014 au 31/05/2015	2812	3975	99	C
1/10/2015 au 31/05/2016	2177	3077	77	B
1/10/2016 au 31/05/2017	2310	3265	81	B

Table D.1 – Degree-Day example (cf. [4]) per year

Energy consumption mark	Energy/ m^2
A	< 50
B	51 à 90
C	91 à 150
D	151 à 230
E	231 à 330
F	331 à 450
G	> 450

Table D.2 – Energy consumption mark according to the French Regulation

Appendix E

Computer and software used

The used computer is a standard laptop PC DELL 64 bits - Ram 8Go - equiped with a Intel (R) Core (TM) i5-3360M CPU 2.80GHz processor, running under Windows 10.

The free software is GNU Octave, version 5.2.0 (<http://www.octave.org>), which is compatible with the commercial software MATLAB (<https://fr.mathworks.com/products/matlab.html>). A great advantage of the two softwares MATLAB and OCTAVE is their matrix structure.

The present document has been edited with the free software LATEX on the free platform TeXworks for Windows (<http://www.tug.org/texworks/>) version 0.6.2.

The running time of a thermal-hydraulic calculation is about 130 secondes for a network including 7 circuits.

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